

Optimizing the Bidding Strategy and Assessing Profitability of Over-Install Renewable Plants Equipped with Battery Energy Storage Systems

Lysandros Tziovani, Lenos Hadjidemetriou, Stelios Timotheou

^aKIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence and the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

Abstract

The over-installation of renewable energy sources (RES) can enhance the profits of RES producers by increasing the total exporting energy; however, RES power curtailments must be applied under over-production of RES plants to ensure their contracted maximum export capacity limits. Battery energy storage systems (BESSs) can be used to reduce the RES curtailments and therefore enhance the profits of producers. This work develops a bidding strategy as a scenario-based stochastic optimization scheme to maximize the expected profits of producers in electricity markets considering battery degradation and maximum export capacity constraints. Using the proposed scheme, a financial analysis is performed to assess the profitability for over-installing hybrid RES plants by calculating the *net present value* and *internal rate of return* of the project under different BESS costs. Simulation results, using real data from a wind and photovoltaic plant, demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed stochastic scheme in enhancing the profit of producers compared to the corresponding deterministic scheme. The performed financial analysis, using the *net present value* metric, indicates that a maximum over-installation of 150% – 170% and 160% – 180% for the wind and photovoltaic plant, respectively, is profitable, while the usage of a BESS is profitable when its cost is under 200,000 €/MWh.

Keywords: battery degradation, bidding strategy, capacity-constrained RES sites, overplanted hybrid RES sites, photovoltaic power plants, wind power plants.

1. Introduction

The penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) into the power systems is expected to increase rapidly in the next years to meet the target of the European Union to become climate-neutral by 2050 [1]. Nevertheless, the high RES generation uncertainty poses significant challenges for system operators to ensure the safe and reliable operation of the power system. This is mainly due to the mismatch between forecasted and actual RES generation, which creates power imbalances in real operation. One promising solution to address the negative effects of intermittent RES generation, such as power imbalances, is the use of battery energy storage systems (BESSs) [2, 3].

The requirement for RES plants to participate in electricity markets presents opportunities to maximize profits by taking advantage of market operations. This includes buying and storing energy when prices are low and selling when prices are high. RES producers who participate in day-ahead energy markets are paid based on their scheduled RES production profile submitted to the market for the next day [4]. However, since day-ahead prices are unknown, producers must make decisions based on forecasted prices, which may reduce their profits in case of high forecasting errors. Additionally, forecasting errors in RES power generation create power imbalances that threaten the stability of the power system. Power imbalances can result in power deficits which are penalized at higher costs compared to day-ahead prices, or power excesses which are paid at lower prices [5]. This incentivizes RES producers to submit accurate scheduled production profiles to the day-ahead market to max-

imize profits. This work aims to develop a bidding strategy for RES-BESS producers to maximize profits by buying and selling power in electricity markets, considering capacity-constrained RES sites and battery degradation.

RES plants can export power into the power grid up to their associated maximum export capacity (MEC), which is imposed by the system operator when a RES owner receives a connection offer [6]. Nevertheless, an over-installation of RES generation facilities can enhance the profits of RES producers by increasing the total exporting energy; however, RES power curtailments must be applied under over-production of RES plants to ensure their contracted MEC. For example, an over-installation of wind generation facilities can increase the wind power output at low wind speeds, but wind power curtailments are required under high wind conditions to satisfy the MEC requirements [7]. Although the over-installation of RES generation plants implies RES curtailments, greater capital investment, and more capital at risk, can increase returns to investors [7]. According to the 2014 Decision on Installed Capacity Cap (ICC) of the Irish Commission for Energy Regulation [8], generators connected to the grid (mainly wind farms) can over-install by up to 20%, i.e., the ICC is set to 120% of the MEC. For example, a wind producer can install a generation capacity up to 12 MW when its contracted MEC is 10 MW, but the power export from the site is limited to 10 MW. According to the 2023 Consultation Paper on ICC [6], the Irish Commission for Regulation of Utilities seeks feedback on relaxing the 120% ICC for both single technology and hybrid technology

sites, i.e., including BESSs, behind a single connection point, without increasing the contracted MEC. A potential increment or removal of the 120% ICC limit may allow for more efficient use of the current infrastructure, reducing the need to upgrade or build network infrastructure, and can benefit hybrid projects to install multiple technologies with different generation profiles [6]. For example, BESSs can be used to store the surplus RES generation to avoid RES curtailments and therefore increase profits by selling the surplus energy when prices are high. However, the consideration of battery degradation costs in bidding and operating strategies in electricity markets is essential to ensure that the revenues obtained from the BESSs operation will at least cover their true operation and maintenance costs [9, 10].

The main battery degradation factors are the calendar and cycle aging [9, 10, 11]. Calendar factors, such as calendar time and ambient temperature, are usually ignored in optimization problems because they do not directly impact the scheduling of BESS charging and discharging power [9, 10]. Cycle factors, such as depth-of-discharge (DoD), over-charge, over-discharge and current rate, are directly related to the charging/discharging scheduling of BESSs. Empirical models derived from experimental data are widely used to capture the most important cycle factors, such as the DoD of the operating cycles [9, 10]. Empirical life loss functions indicate that electrochemical batteries age nonlinearly to the cycle depth [10, 11]. To count BESS cycles and quantify the cumulative impact, the rainflow counting algorithm has been widely used for battery life assessment [10, 12]. However, the rainflow counting algorithm does not have an analytical mathematical expression and cannot be incorporated into optimization formulations [10]. Towards this direction, an approximate cycle-based degradation model that can be easily incorporated in optimization formulations is proposed in [10]. Different degradation models that consider cycle factors and are independent from the rainflow counting algorithm are proposed in [13, 14, 15]; however, the usage of these models in optimization problems results in mixed-integer programs (MIP) which are challenging to solve especially when stochastic optimization problems are considered. In [9, 10], bidding strategies of BESSs participating in electricity markets are developed; however, these works do not consider the combined RES-BESS system.

Day-ahead offering strategies of wind power producers using stochastic programming to consider RES generation, day-ahead price, and imbalance price uncertainties are proposed in [5, 16, 17]. Similarly, an operational bidding strategy is proposed in [18] to optimize the participation of a photovoltaic (PV) power plant in the electricity spot markets, i.e., the day-ahead, intraday, and imbalance markets. However, the works in [5, 16, 17, 18] do not consider the usage of energy storage systems. Day-ahead trading strategies of combined wind generation and pumped-storage units are presented in [19, 20], but the expansion of pumped-storage units is limited due to environmental constraints. Moreover, an offering strategy for coordinated wind power and compressed air energy storage (CAES) in electricity markets is proposed in [21]; however, CAESs have lower efficiency and limited flexibility compared to BESSs. Of-

fering and operating strategies are proposed in [22], but the day-ahead offering strategy is developed as a deterministic optimization problem; thus, the uncertainties in RES generation, day-ahead and imbalance prices are ignored. Day-ahead bidding strategies for wind plants that handle the associated uncertainties are presented in [23, 24, 25]. Similarly, a stochastic bidding strategy for PV-BESS plants in day-ahead and balancing markets is proposed in [26]. Moreover, a bidding strategy of a virtual power plant composed of a PV plant, charging stations for electric vehicles, and a BESS is proposed in [27]. However, none of the aforementioned bidding strategies for RES-BESS producers considers the BESS cycle degradation cost, which can reduce the producers' profit. In addition, the aforementioned works consider capacity-unconstrained RES sites and ignore MEC constraints, which challenge the optimal energy scheduling of the RES-BESS system.

An energy management strategy of an over-install offshore wind farm considering dynamic thermal limits of the export cable is proposed in [28]. Similarly, a methodology to reduce power curtailments from an over-install offshore wind farm considering the thermal limits of the cable is proposed in [29]. Moreover, an optimization scheme is developed in [30] to minimize wind power curtailments considering dynamic thermal limit constraints of the transmission line. However, the works in [28, 29, 30] do not assess the profitability for over-installing RES plants. An investigation study for over-planting (over-installing) in offshore wind power plants in different regulatory regimes is performed in [31]. A similar investigation study is performed in [32] to assess the profitability of over-planting an offshore wind power farm by formulating an optimization problem that maximizes the annual revenue obtained from the wind farm. The study in [7] shows that over-installing wind generation facilities by 8% is profitable under a fixed-price scenario in Great Britain. In [33], a strategy is proposed to find the optimal capacity of a wind plant installation by maximizing the expected profit of the wind plant investment, applying wind power curtailments when the wind power generation exceeds the MEC limits. However, none of the aforementioned works in [7, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33] performs an investigation study to assess the profitability for over-installing hybrid RES-BESS sites.

This work develops a bidding strategy and investigates the profitability for over-install RES-BESS plants (e.g., wind-BESS and PV-BESS). Towards this direction, a scenario-based stochastic optimization problem is developed to maximize the expected profits of producers in electricity markets, considering battery degradation and uncertainty in RES generation, as well as day-ahead and imbalance prices. Considering the over-installation of RES-BESS plants, the proposed scheme limits the maximum power export of RES plants by making BESS decisions which reduce power curtailments during the actual operation of RES-BESS plants, enhancing the profits of producers. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed stochastic scheme in improving producers' profits compared to both the corresponding deterministic scheme and the base scenario, where the RES generation forecasting profile is directly submitted to the market. Moreover, using the proposed

bidding strategy, a financial analysis is performed to investigate the profitability for over-installing hybrid RES-BESS sites by calculating the *internal rate of return* (IRR) and *net present value* (NPV) of the project under different BESS costs. In sum, the main contributions of this work are the following:

1. Development of a bidding strategy for over-install hybrid RES-BESS plants as a scenario-based stochastic optimization problem, considering battery degradation and MEC constraints. The proposed scheme is formulated as a linear program, which can be fast and reliably solved, by dealing with the non-convexities arising from the degradation and power loss models of the BESS.
2. Evaluation of the proposed bidding strategy in two different RES-BESS plants, a wind-BESS and PV-BESS plant, using real data.
3. Performance of a financial analysis to assess the profitability for over-installing a wind-BESS and a PV-BESS plant by estimating the expected return on investment and the net present value of the project using real data.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 states the problem and Section 3 formulates the deterministic bidding strategy as a linear program. Section 4 formulates the scenario-based stochastic optimization scheme. The scenario selection methodology is explained in Section 5. The IRR and NPV financial metrics that are used to evaluate investment projects are presented in Section 6 and simulation results are demonstrated in Section 7. Finally, practical implications and conclusions are given in Sections 8 and 9, respectively.

2. Problem Statement

This section states the underlying problem by (a) describing the constraints of the capacity-constrained RES-BESS plant, (b) presenting the battery degradation model, (c) introducing the framework of the electricity markets under consideration, and (d) formulating the optimization problem of the bidding strategy considering the RES-BESS constraints, degradation model, and electricity market structure.

2.1. RES-BESS Plant

We consider a BESS integrated in a capacity-constrained RES plant (e.g., wind or PV plant), which is connected to the power grid. The arrows in Fig. 1 indicate the possible power flow directions in a RES-BESS plant. Specifically, the power balance is defined as

$$P_t^r + P_t^d - P_t^c = P_t^g, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{T} = \{1, \dots, T\}$ denotes the considered time horizon. Variables $P_t^r \geq 0$, $P_t^d \geq 0$, $P_t^c \geq 0$, and P_t^g denote the RES power generation, BESS discharging power, BESS charging power, and buying (negative) or selling (positive) power into the power grid at time-step t in MW.

Figure 1: The over-install RES-BESS plant under MEC limits.

Considering an over-installation of RES power generation facilities, the power exchange with the grid, P_t^g , is restricted to the imposed MEC limits, defined as

$$-\bar{P}^g \leq P_t^g \leq \bar{P}^g, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (2)$$

where constant \bar{P}^g denotes the MEC limit that is imposed by the system operator when a RES owner receives a connection offer. Considering an over-install RES plant with nominal capacity \bar{P}^r , it is true that $\bar{P}^r \geq \bar{P}^g$ such that $\bar{P}^g = \rho \bar{P}^r$, with $0 < \rho \leq 1$. To ensure the power exchange limits, the BESS can be charged when the RES generation exceeds the MEC limits; otherwise, RES power curtailments, P_t^u , must be applied, defined as

$$P_t^u = P_t^a - P_t^r, \quad 0 \leq P_t^r \leq P_t^a, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3)$$

where constant P_t^a , $0 \leq P_t^a \leq \bar{P}^r$, denotes the available RES generation at time-step t ; P_t^a is usually replaced by the RES generation forecast. In (3), it is true that the RES generation $P_t^r < P_t^a$ when RES curtailments are applied, implying that $P_t^u > 0$.

Considering the widely-used piecewise linear power loss model presented in [34], the energy stored in the BESS is defined as

$$C_{t+1} = C_t + \Delta T(-P_t^d/\eta^d + \eta^c P_t^c), \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (4)$$

where ΔT is the time-step duration in hours, η^c and η^d the charging and discharging efficiency coefficients, and C_t the energy stored in the BESS at time-step t in MWh. The charging and discharging power losses, l^c and l^d in %, are implicitly considered in (4) using the efficiency coefficients, such that $\eta^d = 1/(1 + l^d)$ and $\eta^c = 1 - l^c$. The BESS energy limits are set equal to

$$\underline{C} \leq C_t \leq \bar{C}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (5a)$$

$$C_0 = I, \quad C_{T+1} \geq E^f, \quad (5b)$$

where constants \underline{C} and \bar{C} denote the minimum and maximum energy limits, and I and E^f the initial and final energy stored in the BESS over the considered time horizon, such that $\underline{C} \leq I \leq \bar{C}$ and $\underline{C} \leq E^f \leq \bar{C}$. The charging and discharging power limits are given by

$$0 \leq P_t^d \leq \bar{P}^d, \quad 0 \leq P_t^c \leq \bar{P}^c, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (6a)$$

Figure 2: Identifying the BESS cycle depths for a given SoC profile. The SoC profile has one charging half cycle of 60% DoD (δ_1 - δ_2), one full cycle of 40% DoD (δ_2 - δ_4), and one discharging half cycle of 50% DoD (δ_4 - δ_5).

$$P_t^d P_t^c = 0, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (6b)$$

where constants \bar{P}^d and \bar{P}^c denote the discharging and charging power limits. The non-convex constraint in (6b) ensures non-simultaneous charging and discharging.

2.2. BESS Degradation

The cycle depth is a critical stress factor for BESS degradation which presents a nonlinear aging relationship with respect to the DoD¹ [11]. Specifically, cycles with higher DoD cause more severe damage to the battery. The DoD is associated with the state-of-charge (SoC) which is defined as

$$C_t^S = C_t / \hat{C}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (7)$$

where variable C_t^S denotes the SoC of the BESS at time-step t and constant \hat{C} denotes the nominal BESS capacity in MWh. The rainflow cycle counting method is widely used to identify the BESS cycles for a given SoC profile [10, 12]. Specifically, the main idea of the rainflow cycle method is to find the minimum and maximum values of the SoC profile, identify the half and full cycles, and calculate their DoD. For example, the SoC profile demonstrated in Fig. 2 has one charging half cycle of 60% DoD (δ_1 - δ_2), one full cycle of 40% DoD (δ_2 - δ_4), and one discharging half cycle of 50% DoD (δ_4 - δ_5). Let $\mathcal{J} = \{1, \dots, J\}$ denotes the set of cycles for a given SoC profile, d_j the DoD of cycle $j \in \mathcal{J}$ in %, and $k_j = \{0.5, 1\}$ the length of cycle $j \in \mathcal{J}$, where $k_j = 0.5$ and $k_j = 1$ denote a half and full cycle, respectively. The rainflow algorithm for cycle identification is defined as

$$[\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{d}] = \mathbf{Rainflow}(\mathbf{C}^S), \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{k} denote the vector forms of d_j and k_j , $\forall j \in \mathcal{J}$, while \mathbf{C}^S the vector form of C_t^S , $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$.

Empirical non-linear DoD stress models are used to determine the degradation (also known as life loss) caused by one cycle of a BESS operating under a specific DoD [10, 11]. A widely-used model is represented by the polynomial DoD stress function, $\Phi(d_j)$, given by

$$\Phi(d_j) = \gamma_1 d_j^{\gamma_2}, \quad (9)$$

¹The DoD is defined as the ratio of the amount of energy that has been extracted from the battery in a cycle to its nominal capacity.

Figure 3: BESS degradation in % as a function of the DoD. The convex degradation function is approximated using N piece-wise linear segments.

Figure 4: Prices from the Spanish electricity market for 01/02/2022: (a) day-ahead electricity prices and (b) imbalance prices of the balancing market [35].

where γ_1 and γ_2 denote the parameters of function $\Phi(d_j)$. For example, Fig. 3 depicts the degradation using the polynomial DoD stress function, indicating that cycles with higher DoD cause more severe BESS degradation. For example, a 20% full cycle DoD causes 0.002% degradation, while a 60% full cycle DoD causes 0.019% degradation.

The total degradation, $L(\mathbf{C}^S)$, resulting from an SoC profile is calculated as the sum of the degradation caused by all the half and full cycles, defined as

$$L(\mathbf{C}^S) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} k_j \Phi(d_j). \quad (10)$$

The total degradation cost, $F^D(\mathbf{C}^S)$, is usually calculated as the product of the total degradation, $L(\mathbf{C}^S)$, and the battery replacement cost R [10], as

$$F^D(\mathbf{C}^S) = L(\mathbf{C}^S)R. \quad (11)$$

2.3. Electricity Markets

The profits of RES-BESS producers can be maximized by trading energy in electricity markets. This work considers both the day-ahead (DA) and balancing markets.

Day-ahead market. The DA market concerns the entire day D and is cleared the day before, i.e. $D - 1$. Fig. 4(a) illustrates the hourly day-ahead prices, λ_t^D , obtained from the Spanish electricity market for the day 01/02/2022. The figure indicates that RES-BESS producers can benefit from energy arbitrage by buying and storing power during low-price periods and selling power during high-price periods. Since the actual DA prices

are unknown when RES-BESS producers submit their bids to the DA market, producers can maximize their expected profits by making energy trading decisions based on predictions of the DA market prices and RES power generation.

Balancing market. Having a perfect next-day forecast for the RES power generation is unrealistic, due to the intermittent uncertain nature of these sources. As a result, any mismatch between day-ahead scheduled and actual power generation of the RES-BESS plant creates power imbalances during actual operation. These power imbalances can either cause excess or deficit of power in case of over-production or under-production of the RES-BESS plant, respectively. Considering the Spanish electricity market, the producer will be paid (charged) for its excess (deficit) of generation according to the imbalance prices of the balancing market. Fig. 4(b) depicts the imbalance prices for power excess, λ_t^+ , and power deficit, λ_t^- , for the day 01/02/2022. The figure indicates that $\lambda_t^+ \leq \lambda_t^D$ and $\lambda_t^- \geq \lambda_t^D$, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$. Therefore, the imbalance prices for excess and deficit of power can be linked with the day-ahead prices [5] as

$$r_t^+ = \frac{\lambda_t^+}{\lambda_t^D} \leq 1, \quad r_t^- = \frac{\lambda_t^-}{\lambda_t^D} \geq 1, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (12)$$

where r_t^+ and r_t^- denote the imbalance price ratio for excess and deficit of power, respectively. According to (12), over-production is paid at a lower price compared to the DA price, while under-production is charged at a higher price. This incentivizes RES-BESS producers to reduce their power imbalances to maximize their profits.

2.4. Bidding Strategy

The bidding strategy aims to maximize the expected profits of RES-BESS producers by determining the power exchange with the grid through the day-ahead energy scheduling of the capacity-constrained RES-BESS plant. The outcome of the bidding strategy is the power exchange with the grid submitted to the DA market. This work considers *price-taker² producers*.

Assuming perfect knowledge of the RES generation, P_t^a , and day-ahead electricity prices, λ_t^D , any power imbalances are eliminated and the balancing market can be ignored. Under this assumption, the bidding strategy is formulated as a deterministic optimization problem that maximizes (minimizes) the revenues (costs) of selling (buying) energy in the DA market and minimizes the BESS degradation cost, while satisfying the dynamics and physical constraints of the capacity-constrained RES-BESS plant, as

$$\text{maximize} \quad \Delta T \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \lambda_t^D P_t^s - F^D(\mathbf{C}^S), \quad (13a)$$

$$\text{subject to:} \quad (1) - (8). \quad (13b)$$

Problem (13) is challenging to solve for three reasons:

1. *Non-convex BESS power loss model.* The complementarity constraint (6b) of the BESS power loss model is non-convex as it involves a product of variables.

²A price-taker producer has no capability of altering market-clearing prices and takes the prevailing market prices (see [36], Section 7.3).

2. *Rainflow algorithm.* Although the polynomial DoD stress model in (9) is convex, the rainflow counting algorithm (8) does not have an analytical mathematical expression and cannot be incorporated into an optimization formulation [10].

3. *Parametric Uncertainty.* Assuming perfect knowledge of RES generation and day-ahead electricity prices for the next day is unrealistic; thus, the actual RES generation, P_t^a , and DA prices, λ_t^D , are uncertain. Nonetheless, having uncertainty in RES generation implies that the balancing market should also be considered in the bidding strategy which implies that the imbalance ratios r_t^+ and r_t^- should also be treated as uncertain.

In the next section, we develop a linear deterministic optimization formulation to deal with the non-convexities arising from the first two challenges, while in Section 4 we develop a scenario-based stochastic optimization bidding strategy to handle the aforementioned uncertainties.

3. Deterministic Bidding Strategy

This section formulates the deterministic bidding strategy as a linear program, which can be fast and reliably solved, by incorporating an approximate BESS degradation model and using a relaxed power loss model.

3.1. Relaxed Power Loss Model

Constraints (6a)-(6b) of the non-convex power loss model can be reformulated using binary variables, yielding

$$0 \leq P_t^d \leq (1 - b_t) \bar{P}^d, \quad 0 \leq P_t^c \leq b_t \bar{P}^c, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (14a)$$

$$b_t \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (14b)$$

where binary variable b_t is used in (14a) to ensure non-simultaneous charging and discharging. The relaxed model is derived by relaxing b_t to take continuous values, i.e.

$$b_t \in [0, 1], \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (15)$$

The relaxed model, i.e. constraints (4)-(5b), (14a), and (15), can be used to formulate convex optimization problems. This model is exact, generating the optimal solution when charging and discharging do not simultaneously occur. In the proposed bidding strategy, the maximization of the producer profit is an incentive to satisfy the relaxation exactness, as simultaneous charging and discharging increase the BESS power losses [37] and hence reduce the stored energy in the BESS which can be sold to the grid according to (1).

3.2. Approximate BESS Degradation Model

To deal with the rainflow counting algorithm (8), which cannot be incorporated in a convex mathematical program, we utilize the approximate linear degradation model proposed in [10]. This model is derived by eliminating the rainflow algorithm and

approximating the degradation function (9) using piecewise linear segments. The rainflow algorithm is eliminated by assuming that degradation only occurs during the discharging period of the BESS, such that one discharging half cycle is counted as one full cycle of the same DoD. Thus, the charging half cycles are ignored. This is a reasonable assumption when we consider the daily BESS operation in electricity markets because the charging and discharging half cycles are almost the same [10]. For example, considering the SoC profile shown in Fig. 2, the total degradation using the approximate model and rainflow algorithm is equal to $L(\mathbf{C}^S) = \Phi(40\%) + \Phi(50\%)$ and $L(\mathbf{C}^S) = \Phi(40\%) + 0.5\Phi(50\%) + 0.5\Phi(60\%)$, respectively. As a result, the approximation error is equal to $|0.5\Phi(50\%) - 0.5\Phi(60\%)|$ which is relatively small compared to the total degradation.

Degradation Cost Function. The convex DoD stress function, $\Phi(d_j)$, is approximated using a piecewise linear function with $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ linear segments, as shown in Fig. 3 with $N = 3$. The degradation cost function of the approximate model is defined as

$$F^A(\mathbf{P}^{d,A}) = \Delta T \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{n=1}^N c_n^A P_{t,n}^{d,A}, \quad (16)$$

where variable $P_{t,n}^{d,A} \geq 0$ denotes the BESS discharging power for time-step $t \in \mathcal{T}$ and linear segment $n \in \mathcal{N}$, $\mathbf{P}^{d,A}$ the vector form of $P_{t,n}^{d,A}$, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}$, and constant c_n^A the degradation cost associated with DoD segment $n \in \mathcal{N}$. Constant c_n^A is calculated for each segment $n \in \mathcal{N}$ using the degradation function $\Phi(d_j)$, replacement cost R , discharging efficiency η^d , and BESS capacity \hat{C} [10], as

$$c_n^A = \frac{R}{\eta^d \hat{C}} N \left(\Phi\left(\frac{n}{N}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{n-1}{N}\right) \right). \quad (17)$$

Constraints. Considering the set of linear segments \mathcal{N} , the approximate model reformulates constraint (4) as, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}$,

$$C_{t+1,n}^A = C_{t,n}^A + \Delta T (-P_{t,n}^{d,A} / \eta^d + \eta^c P_{t,n}^{c,A}), \quad (18)$$

where variables $P_{t,n}^{c,A} \geq 0$, and $C_{t,n}^A \geq 0$ denote the charging power and energy stored in the BESS for each time interval $t \in \mathcal{T}$ and DoD segment $n \in \mathcal{N}$. The energy limit of each DoD segment is set as

$$C_{t,n}^A \leq \bar{C}_n^A, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, n \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (19a)$$

$$C_{1,n}^A = I_n^A, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (19b)$$

where constants \bar{C}_n^A and I_n^A denote the maximum and initial energy stored in the BESS in segment n , respectively. Considering that all DoD segments have the same energy limits, then it is true that $\bar{C}_n^A = \hat{C}/N$, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$. The total discharging/charging power and energy stored in the BESS at time t are equal to

$$P_t^d = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} P_{t,n}^{d,A}, \quad P_t^c = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} P_{t,n}^{c,A}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (20a)$$

$$C_t = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} C_{t,n}^A, \quad \underline{C} \leq C_t \leq \bar{C}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (20b)$$

The constraints presented in (5b), (14a), (15) are also included in the model. Since the degradation cost function is convex monotonically increasing, it is true that $c_n^A \leq c_{n+1}^A$. This implies that the BESS always discharges from the DoD segments with the lower degradation cost to the segments with higher cost.

3.3. Mathematical Formulation

The deterministic optimization problem (13) is reformulated to consider the approximate BESS degradation model and relaxed power loss model. In addition, the actual RES generation P_t^g and day-ahead prices λ_t^D , which are unknown, are replaced by their predicted values \hat{P}_t^g and $\hat{\lambda}_t^D$, respectively, such that \hat{P}_t^g is used in (3) instead of P_t^g . The considered problem, defined as Problem \mathcal{P}^D , is formulated as

$$\mathcal{P}^D : \begin{cases} \text{maximize} & \Delta T \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (\hat{\lambda}_t^D P_t^g - F^A(\mathbf{P}^{d,A})) \\ \text{subject to} & (1) - (3), (5b), (14a), (15), (18) - (20b). \end{cases} \quad (20b)$$

Problem \mathcal{P}^D is a linear program.

4. Stochastic Bidding Strategy

This section builds on the formulation of the deterministic bidding strategy of Section 3 to develop a two-stage scenario-based stochastic optimization scheme to deal with uncertainties in RES generation, day-ahead prices, and imbalance ratios. Towards this direction, scenario curves are used to characterize each uncertainty source, where a scenario curve represents one possible realization of the corresponding uncertainty source, e.g., day-ahead RES generation. The proposed scenario-based stochastic scheme involves two stages of decision-making. Decisions are made in the day-ahead market (first stage) considering possible scenarios of the balancing market (second stage). The first-stage decision variables are scenario-independent and determine the scheduling of the RES-BESS plant for the next day, i.e., P_t^g , P_t^r , P_t^d and P_t^c . The second-stage decision variables are scenario-dependent and alleviate power imbalances caused by different uncertainty realizations.

4.1. Objective Function

We consider the set of scenarios $\mathcal{S} = \{1, \dots, S\}$ with $S = |\mathcal{S}|$; each scenario concerns the RES power generation, day-ahead prices, and imbalance ratios of the considered horizon \mathcal{T} . Let variables $P_{t,s}^+ \geq 0$ and $P_{t,s}^- \geq 0$ denote the imbalance power for excess and deficit of power at time-step t of scenario s , respectively. The objective of the stochastic optimization scheme is to maximize the producer profit by maximizing the expected market profit, $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{P}^g, \mathbf{P}^+, \mathbf{P}^-)]$, and minimizing the BESS degradation cost, $F^A(\mathbf{P}^{d,A})$, yielding

$$\text{maximize} \quad \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{P}^g, \mathbf{P}^+, \mathbf{P}^-)] - F^A(\mathbf{P}^{d,A}), \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{P}^g , \mathbf{P}^+ , and \mathbf{P}^- are the vector-forms of variables P_t^g , $P_{t,s}^+$, and $P_{t,s}^-$, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$, $s \in \mathcal{S}$. The expected market profit is defined

as the weighted-average profit³ of the producer obtained from the day-ahead and balancing markets across all scenarios

$$\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{P}^g, \mathbf{P}^+, \mathbf{P}^-)] = \Delta T \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \phi_s \left(\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (\tilde{\lambda}_{t,s}^D P_t^g + \tilde{r}_{t,s}^+ \tilde{\lambda}_{t,s}^D P_{t,s}^+ - \tilde{r}_{t,s}^- \tilde{\lambda}_{t,s}^D P_{t,s}^-) \right), \quad (22)$$

where constants $\tilde{\lambda}_{t,s}^D$, $\tilde{r}_{t,s}^+$, and $\tilde{r}_{t,s}^-$ denote the day-ahead prices and imbalance price ratios for excess and deficit of power at time-step t of scenario s , respectively; ϕ_s is the weighting parameter of scenario s such that $\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \phi_s = 1$. Note that the scenario selection process is explained in Section 5.

4.2. Constraints

First-Stage Constraints. The constraints of the day-ahead stage, which are scenario independent, are associated with the constraints of the deterministic bidding strategy, given by

$$\text{Constraints: } (1), (5b), (14a), (15), (18) - (20b). \quad (23)$$

The RES power generation, P_t^r , is limited by the nominal capacity of the RES plant, \bar{P}^r , defined as

$$0 \leq P_t^r \leq \bar{P}^r, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (24)$$

In the stochastic optimization scheme, the produced power P_t^r , $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$ is a first-stage variable defined by the RES power production profiles of the selected scenarios.

Second-Stage Constraints. The constraints of the power exchange limits (MEC limits) in (2) are reformulated to consider the power imbalances for power excess, $P_{t,s}^+$, and deficit, $P_{t,s}^-$, in scenario s as

$$P_t^g + P_{t,s}^+ \leq \bar{P}^g, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (25a)$$

$$-\bar{P}^g \leq P_t^g - P_{t,s}^-, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (25b)$$

Constraints (25a) and (25b) ensure the direct and reverse power flow limits, respectively. Any over-production or under-production of the RES power generation needs to be compensated to ensure power balance. Let constant $\tilde{P}_{t,s}^r$ denote the RES power generation at time t of scenario s . Then, the difference between the RES generation of scenario s and the scheduled RES generation at time t , $(\tilde{P}_{t,s}^r - P_t^r)$, denotes the RES over-production (positive) or under-production (negative). When $(\tilde{P}_{t,s}^r - P_t^r) > 0$ the RES over-production creates excess of power, $P_{t,s}^+$, that will be paid, except of the cases where the power exchange limits in (25a) are violated and RES power curtailments, $\hat{P}_{t,s}^u$, must be applied. Similarly, when $(\tilde{P}_{t,s}^r - P_t^r) < 0$ the RES under-production creates deficit of power, $P_{t,s}^-$, that will be charged. These conditions yield

$$(\tilde{P}_{t,s}^r - P_t^r) = P_{t,s}^+ - P_{t,s}^- + \hat{P}_{t,s}^u, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (26)$$

Note that the BESS power set-points are first-stage decisions that can adjust the scheduled grid power, P_t^g , through (1) to reduce the RES power curtailments, $\hat{P}_{t,s}^u$, in (26). It is important to

note that non-convex constraints that ensure non-simultaneous excess and deficit of power can be avoided [5], because the expected market profit in (22) is maximized when $P_{t,s}^-$ is minimized, implying that $P_{t,s}^+ P_{t,s}^- = 0$ when $\tilde{r}_{t,s}^+ < \tilde{r}_{t,s}^-$, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}, s \in \mathcal{S}$.

The optimization problem of the stochastic bidding strategy of the capacity-constrained RES-BESS plant, defined as Problem \mathcal{P}^S , is summarized as

$$\mathcal{P}^S : \begin{cases} \text{maximize} & (21) \\ \text{subject to} & (23) - (26). \end{cases}$$

Problem \mathcal{P}^S is a linear program that can be fast and reliably solved under a large number of scenarios.

5. Scenario Selection

This section explains the methodology used to select scenario curves for the RES power generation (whether it is from PV or wind), day-ahead prices, and imbalance ratios. This work selects the scenario curves for each uncertainty source based on historical data, using two different methodologies.

Methodology 1. The first methodology assumes that forecasting data for the next day are available for the considered uncertainty source, e.g., for the wind power generation. This method selects a subset of the historical curves which are closest to the day-ahead forecasted curve. Towards this direction, we utilize the Euclidean distance between a historical and the forecasted curve, given by [38]

$$y_k(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{A}_k) = \sqrt{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (W_t - A_{t,k})^2}, \quad k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (27)$$

where \mathbf{W} is the time series vector of the forecasted curve, \mathbf{A}_k , $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$ is the time series vector of the k th historical actual curves, and \mathcal{K} is the corresponding set. Then, the set of selected curves $\mathcal{G} = \{1, \dots, G\}$ is formed by the $G - 1$ curves with the smallest Euclidean distance and the forecasted curve. The weights of the selected curves are weighted according to an importance factor $f_g^G \in [0, 1]$, $\forall g \in \mathcal{G}$ that aims to put more importance on curves with small Euclidean distance. Factor f_g^G is defined as

$$f_g^G = 1 - \frac{y_g(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{A}_g)}{y^{max}}, \quad g \in \mathcal{G}, \quad (28)$$

where $y^{max} = \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \{y_k(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{A}_k)\}$. Note that the importance factor of the forecasted curve \mathbf{W} is equal to one because the corresponding Euclidean distance is equal to zero. Normalizing the importance factors yields the weights of the selected curves ϕ_g^G , defined as

$$\phi_g^G = f_g^G / \sum_{i \in \mathcal{G}} f_i^G, \quad g \in \mathcal{G}. \quad (29)$$

Methodology 2. The second methodology assumes that forecasting data for the next day are unavailable for the considered uncertainty source. Thus, only historical data of the previous days are used to form the scenarios. Let day D denote the current day and $D + 1$ the day ahead where we aim to determine the

³The market profits are defined as the market revenues minus the costs.

Figure 5: (a) The structure of the two-stage scenario tree that is considered in the stochastic Problem \mathcal{P}^S and (b) the selection of each scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ as a combination of a single RES generation, day-ahead price, and imbalance ratio curve.

scheduled grid power, $P_t^g \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$, submitted to the day-ahead market. We assume that the decisions are made at the end of day D , enabling the use of the actual curve of this day. Then, the set of selected curves $\mathcal{G} = \{D - G + 1, \dots, D\}$ is formed by the historical curves of the last G days. The importance factor $\mathbf{f}^G = [1/G, 2/G, \dots, G/G]$ is introduced, aiming to assign an increasing importance on daily profiles closer to day D . Similarly with the first methodology, the weights of the selected curves are defined using (29), where f_g^G is the g element of vector \mathbf{f}^G .

Using either the first or second methodology, depending on the availability of forecasting data, we select

- V RES generation curves with weights $\phi_v^V, v = 1, \dots, V$.
- M day-ahead price curves with weights $\phi_m^M, m = 1, \dots, M$.
- Q imbalance ratio curves with weights $\phi_q^Q, q = 1, \dots, Q$.

The methodologies used in this work for selecting the scenario curves are purely data driven (without considering distributional assumptions). Specifically, the first methodology is based on the forecast-based scenario-tree generation method [39] which focus on the situation where the only (or the best) information about the future values of stochastic parameters comes in the form of a forecast and the forecaster does not provide information about the uncertainty. Therefore, considering only forecasted and historical data, this method aims to find periods with forecasts or observations similar to the current forecasts and use data from those periods as extra scenarios. There are also various sophisticated methodologies available in the literature for generating scenarios, such as seasonal

ARIMA and second-order autoregressive models for generating price and wind generation scenarios [5, 36]. Note that the proposed stochastic optimization model, \mathcal{P}^S , is general and can be used with any type of scenario-generation method that creates scenario curves for the RES generation, day-ahead prices, and imbalance ratio. However, the selection of the optimal scenario-generation method for the considered application is out of the scope of this work.

Fig. 5(a) illustrates the structure of the two-stage scenario tree that is considered in the stochastic Problem \mathcal{P}^S , where decisions are made in the day-ahead market (first stage) considering possible scenarios of the balancing market (second stage) [27, 36]. Similarly with [5], any correlations among market prices and RES generation are ignored in this work. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 5(b), we select each scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ as a combination of a single RES generation, day-ahead price, and imbalance ratio curve with weight $\phi_s = \phi_v^V \cdot \phi_m^M \cdot \phi_q^Q$. Thus, the total number of scenarios is $S = V \cdot M \cdot Q$.

In the deterministic scheme, Problem \mathcal{P}^D , the prediction data used depends on the availability of forecasting data for each uncertainty source. Specifically, either the forecasted curve or the historical curve of the previous day D is used as the predicted curve.

6. Investment Criteria

This section presents the financial metrics that are used to assess the profitability of over-install RES-BESS plants. The *net present value* and *internal rate of return* are the most widely-used techniques for evaluating investment projects (see [40], Chapter 5). The NPV is defined as the difference between a project's present value and its cost; therefore, projects with positive NPV are profitable (the highest the better), while projects with negative NPV must be rejected [40]. The present value of a project, Υ , is expressed as the summation of the discounted cash flows over the project life (see [40], Chapter 2), given by

$$\Upsilon = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \frac{\chi_i}{(1 + \mu)^i}, \quad (30)$$

where $\mathcal{I} = \{1, \dots, I\}$ denotes the expected lifetime of the project in years, χ_i denotes the expected annual cash flows for the year $i, i \in \mathcal{I}$, and μ the discount rate or opportunity cost of capital. The opportunity cost is the return that is foregone by investing in the project rather than investing in financial markets. According to the review performed in [40] for the capital market history (see [40], Chapter 7), the returns to investors have varied according to the risks. Specifically, very safe securities, e.g., U.S. Treasury bills, have provided an average return of 4%, while riskiest securities such as stock market provided an average return of 11.1%. For example, the present value of the annual cash flows $\{1000, 1000, 1000\}$ over a 3-year lifetime is $\{952.4, 907.0, 863.8\}$ and $\Upsilon = 2723.2$ when $\mu = 5\%$. The NPV is calculated as

$$\text{NPV} = \Upsilon - \Xi, \quad (31)$$

where Ξ denotes the investment cost. Note that the calculation of the NPV for an over-install RES-BESS plant implies the es-

timination of the annual cash flows of the project, which can be calculated using the proposed bidding strategy.

The IRR is defined as the rate of discount that makes the NPV equal to zero (see [40], Chapter 5), given by

$$\sum_{i \in I} \frac{\chi_i}{(1 + \text{IRR})^i} - \Xi = 0. \quad (32)$$

The IRR indicates the annual expected rate of return from investing in the project (the higher the better). An investment project should be accepted when the IRR is higher than the opportunity cost of capital (μ), considering an equivalent-risk investment in the capital market (see [40]).

7. Simulation Results

This section evaluates the performance of the proposed stochastic bidding strategy of the capacity-constrained RES-BESS plant, considering both PV-BESS and wind-BESS plants. In addition, using the proposed strategy, the profitability for over-installing a wind-BESS and a PV-BESS plant is investigated by estimating the IRR and NPV of the project. The performance of the deterministic and stochastic optimization schemes, Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S , in terms of actual producer profits⁴ is compared with the solution of the following problems:

- **Problem \mathcal{P}^B :** The base case where the BESS is ignored and the predicted RES power generation, \hat{P}_t^a , $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$, is submitted to the day-ahead market.
- **Problem \mathcal{P}^I :** The ideal case where the actual RES power generation, P_t^a , and day-ahead prices, λ_t^D , are used in \mathcal{P}^D . Although Problem \mathcal{P}^I is unrealizable as it assumes knowledge of future information, it is used for comparison purposes as it provides the optimal performance.

All problems are coded in Matlab and solved using optimization solver Gurobi [41] on a personal computer with 16 GB RAM and an Intel Core-i7 2.11 GHz processor. The horizon is set to one day with 30-minute time intervals. The scenarios in Problem \mathcal{P}^S are constructed by selecting 15 curves for RES power generation ($V = 15$) and 10 curves for day-ahead price and imbalance ratio curves ($M = 10$ and $Q = 10$), yielding $S = 1500$ scenarios. All the day-ahead and imbalance price curves are obtained from the Spanish electricity market [35]. This work considers the lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (Li(NiMnCo)O₂) battery as described in [10], where the parameters of the polynomial DoD stress function in (9) are $\gamma_1 = 5.24 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\gamma_2 = 2.03$. Note that various lithium-ion batteries, e.g., Li(NiMnCo)O₂, lithium iron phosphate battery (LiFePO₄), and lithium ion manganese oxide battery (LMO),

⁴The actual producer profits are calculated using the optimization decisions of the RES-BESS plant and the actual RES generation, day-ahead prices, and imbalance ratios. Specifically, the market profits are calculated using the scheduled grid power, while the BESS degradation cost is calculated by applying the BESS decisions in the Rainflow algorithm.

Figure 6: The predicted, actual, and scenario curves used for the performance evaluation of Problems \mathcal{P}^S and \mathcal{P}^D for 04/03/2022: (a) wind power generation (MW), (b) day-ahead prices (€/MWh), (c) imbalance ratio for power deficit, and (d) imbalance ratio for power excess.

differ in their aging mechanisms and cycle life due to their different electrode materials [11]. Although this work considers the Li(NiMnCo)O₂ battery, different batteries with their corresponding DoD stress functions and coefficients can be also used in the derived Problems \mathcal{P}^D , \mathcal{P}^S , and \mathcal{P}^I . $N = 50$ piecewise linear segments are considered in the approximate degradation model. Unless otherwise specified, the battery capital cost is set equal to 100000 €/MWh [42], such that $R = 100000 \times \hat{C}$ €.

7.1. Wind-BESS Producer

Setup. The performance of the proposed stochastic scheme is evaluated using real data from a 10.8 MW ($\bar{P}^r = 10.8$ MW) wind power plant located in Larnaca, Cyprus. The proposed scheme is examined under power exchange limits due to the imposed MEC limits, setting $\bar{P}^s = 9.45$ MW ($\rho = 0.875$) to consider an over-install wind power plant with nominal capacity of 114.28% of MEC. We consider an integrated BESS with capacity of 10 MWh ($\hat{C} = 10$ MWh), charging/discharging power of 10 MW ($\bar{P}^c = \bar{P}^d = 10$ MW) and one-way efficiency of 96% ($\eta^d = \eta^c = 0.96$). Moreover, minimum and maximum energy limits of 1.5 and 9.5 MWh ($\underline{C} = 0.15\hat{C}$ and $\bar{C} = 0.95\hat{C}$ MWh) are set to protect the BESS from over-discharge and over-charge. The initial and final energy stored in the BESS is set to 2 MWh ($I = E^f = 0.2\hat{C}$). Since forecasting data for the wind generation are available and provided from the real wind plant, the corresponding scenario curves are selected using Methodology 1 described in Section 5. The scenario curves for the day-ahead energy prices and imbalance ratios are selected according to Methodology 2 because forecasting data are unavailable.

Performance Evaluation. The performance of the proposed stochastic scheme \mathcal{P}^S is evaluated and compared with the deterministic scheme \mathcal{P}^D for the day 04/03/2022. Fig. 6 depicts the real curves of the wind power generation, day-ahead prices, and imbalance ratios used in the two schemes. Specifically, the

predicted and scenario curves are used as input in \mathcal{P}^S , while only the predicted curves are used in \mathcal{P}^D . Moreover, the actual curves are used for evaluation.

Ignoring the BESS degradation model in Problems \mathcal{P}^S and \mathcal{P}^D , Figs. 7(a)-(d) and 7(e)-(h) illustrate the scheduled day-ahead decisions of the wind-BESS plant as well as the actual system operation using \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S , respectively. As expected, Fig. 7(a) shows that the scheduled wind power follows the predicted curve in \mathcal{P}^D , while Fig. 7(e) indicates that the scheduled wind power deviates from the predicted curve due to the impact of the scenarios in \mathcal{P}^S . Figs. 7(b) and 7(f) demonstrate the scheduled grid power based on the scheduled wind power and the decisions of the BESS power set-points presented in Figs. 7(c) and 7(g). The energy stored in the BESS based on the BESS power set-points is depicted in Figs. 7(d) and 7(h). As shown in Figs. 7(d) and 7(h), two full cycles of almost 80% DoD are presented in both Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S because the BESS degradation is ignored. However, this BESS operation causes a severe BESS degradation, resulting in 0.0646% and 0.0667% degradation and 646.4€ and 667.4€ degradation cost using \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S , respectively. As expected, the uncertainty-aware decisions of Problem \mathcal{P}^S increase the actual producer profit by 2.34% compared to \mathcal{P}^D , where the daily profits using \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S are 35294.3€ and 36120.9€, respectively.

Considering the BESS degradation model, Figs. 8(a)-(c) and 8(d)-(f) illustrate the scheduled and actual grid power, as well as the BESS power and energy decisions using Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S , respectively. To ensure the power exchange limits in actual operation of the wind-BESS plant, wind energy curtailments⁵ of 6.08 MWh and 2.92 MWh are applied in \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S , respectively. As expected, the uncertainty-aware decisions of Problem \mathcal{P}^S reduce the wind curtailments by 51.97%. As shown in Figs. 8(c) and 8(f), both \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S avoid to fully charge the BESS, reducing the degradation from 0.0646% and 0.0667% to 0.0193% and 0.0090% compared to the BESS operation presented in Figs. 7(d) and 7(h). Therefore, the degradation cost in Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S reduces from 646.4€ and 667.4€ to 193.3€ and 90€, respectively. Reducing the degradation cost, the actual producer profit in \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S increases from 35294.3€ and 36120.9€ to 35389.8€ and 36931.5€, respectively. Considering BESS degradation, Problem \mathcal{P}^S increases the producer profit from 2.34% to 4.35% compared to \mathcal{P}^D .

The approximate degradation model yields degradation costs of 208.2€ and 88.1€ for \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S , respectively. These degradation costs are similar to the costs calculated using the Rainflow algorithm (193.3€ and 90€), indicating that the approximation error of the proposed bidding strategy is small (7.7% and 2.1%, respectively).

The execution times of \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S are 0.08 and 14.7 seconds when the BESS degradation model is used, indicating the increased complexity of Problem \mathcal{P}^S compared to \mathcal{P}^D . How-

Figure 7: The scheduled day-ahead decisions of the wind-BESS plant as well as the actual system operation using Problems \mathcal{P}^D (a)-(d) and \mathcal{P}^S (e)-(h) when the BESS degradation is ignored in both optimization problems.

ever, Problem \mathcal{P}^S presents a small execution time despite the consideration of a large number of scenarios ($S = 1500$).

Aggregate Performance Evaluation. The proposed stochastic scheme, Problem \mathcal{P}^S , is evaluated and compared with Problems \mathcal{P}^B , \mathcal{P}^D , and \mathcal{P}^I for each day of the period 01/02/2022-30/09/2022. Table 1 presents the total producer profits and wind power curtailments for the entire period using the considered problems. Interestingly, the actual wind power curtailments using Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S are higher compared to \mathcal{P}^B , where the BESS is not utilized. This is because Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S operate the wind-BESS system closer to the power exchange limits (MEC) to maximize profits through energy storage arbitrage. As a result, wind curtailments occur more frequently in real operation to ensure the power exchange limits when high forecasting errors occur. Although both Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S increase wind curtailments, they also increase the total profit by 0.6% and 5.9%, respectively, compared to \mathcal{P}^B . The Table also indicates the superiority of Problem \mathcal{P}^S to achieve higher profits compared to \mathcal{P}^D , increasing the total profit by 141,665 €. Note that by employing an operating strategy along with the bidding strategy can lead to a significant reduction in actual wind curtailments, resulting in further improvement in the producer profit. Although Problem \mathcal{P}^I assumes perfect knowledge

⁵We consider that RES power curtailments are applied in real operation to maintain the actual power exchange within its MEC limits.

Figure 8: The scheduled day-ahead decisions and actual operation of the wind-BESS plant using Problems \mathcal{P}^D (a)-(c) and \mathcal{P}^S (d)-(f) when the BESS degradation is considered in both optimization problems.

Table 1: Total actual producer profits and wind curtailments for the period 01/02/2022-30/09/2022 using the different problems.

Problem	Profit (€)	Profit increm. (%)	wind curtail. (MWh)
\mathcal{P}^B	2,677,715		332.5
\mathcal{P}^D	2,693,783	0.6	569.6
\mathcal{P}^S	2,835,448	5.9	373.7
\mathcal{P}^I	3,190,269	19.1	58.0

Table 2: Total degradation costs for the period 01/02/2022-30/09/2022 using the approximate degradation model and Rainflow algorithm for Problem \mathcal{P}^S .

	Aprpr. model	Rainflow alg.	Aprpr. error (%)
Degr. cost (€)	44,378	47,103	5.78

of the wind power generation, wind power curtailments of 58 MWh are applied because the BESS capacity is insufficient to always ensure the power exchange limits. Problem \mathcal{P}^I increases the total profit by 19.1% as it provides the optimal performance; however, Problem \mathcal{P}^I is unrealizable. Figs. 6(a) and 6(c)-(d) indicate that the representative scenarios capture the actual curves well; however, this is not the case for the day-ahead prices (see Fig. 6(c)) because by using the historical curves of the previous days as scenarios does not always represent uncertainty well. Thus, by selecting the scenarios in a more sophisticated way can further enhance the performance of Problem \mathcal{P}^S .

Table 2 shows the total degradation cost obtained using the

Figure 9: The investment cost of the wind-BESS plant under different over-installation sizes when the BESS cost is 50,000, 100,000, 200,000, and 300,000 €/MWh, as well as when the BESS is ignored.

approximate degradation model as well as the total degradation cost calculated using the Rainflow algorithm for Problem \mathcal{P}^S for the period 01/02/2022-30/09/2022. As shown in Table 2, the approximate degradation model yields a total degradation costs of 44,378€ which is similar to the cost calculated using the Rainflow algorithm, 47,103€, indicating that the approximation error of the proposed bidding strategy in terms of degradation cost is small, 5.78%.

Over-installation Financial Analysis. The profitability for over-installing the wind-BESS plant is investigated by calculating the IRR and NPV of the project under different over-installation sizes of the wind plant. Towards this direction, the actual annual market profits for wind over-installation sizes of 100%, 110%, 120%, 130%, 140%, 150%, 160%, 170%, 180%, 190%, and 200%, when the MEC limit is 10.8 MW ($\bar{P}^S = 10.8$), are calculated by solving Problems \mathcal{P}^I and \mathcal{P}^S for each day of the period 01/01/2022-31/12/2022. To calculate the NPV and IRR, we consider a total wind installation cost of 1,250,000 €/MW with an annual maintenance cost of 40,000 €/MW [43]. Although the expected lifetime of the wind plant exceeds the 10 years, we assume an investment period of 10 years for the combined wind-BESS system [44] with constant annual cash flows over the years. Specifically, the cash flows are calculated as the difference between the annual market profits of 2022 and annual maintenance costs. Assuming a relatively safe investment, we consider an opportunity cost of capital of $\mu = 5\%$ (see Section 6). The considered investigation is performed for four different BESS costs of 50,000 €/MWh, 100,000 €/MWh, 200,000 €/MWh, and 300,000 €/MWh with an annual maintenance cost of 4,500 €/MWh [44]. Fig. 9 depicts the total investment costs that are used for the calculation of the NPV and IRR for the different over-installation sizes and BESS costs.

The NPV and IRR calculated using Problem \mathcal{P}^I for the different BESS costs and over-installation sizes of the wind plant are demonstrated in Figs. 10(a)-(b). Note that the NPV and IRR are calculated using Problem \mathcal{P}^I as it provides the optimal perfor-

Figure 10: The NPV and IRR using Problems \mathcal{P}^I (a)-(b) and \mathcal{P}^S (c)-(d) under different over-installation sizes when the BESS cost is 50,000, 100,000, 200,000, and 300,000 €/MWh, as well as when the BESS is ignored.

mance; however, Problem \mathcal{P}^I is unrealizable. Fig. 10(a) shows that the increment of the over-installation size from 100% to 160% increases the NPV from 15 to 18.2 million euros when the BESS is ignored, indicating the profitability of the over-installation despite the fact that the IRR is reduced (see Fig. 10(b)) due to the increment of the investment cost. As shown in Figs. 10(a)-(b), an over-installation exceeding 160% must be avoided when the BESS is ignored due to the reduction of both NPV and IRR values. Note that the NPV is reduced under large over-installation sizes, i.e. from 160% to 200%, due to the high RES curtailments, applied to satisfy the MEC limits, that reduce the market profits. Fig. 10(a) also shows that the maximum NPV is obtained for an over-installation size of 170% – 180% when the BESS is considered (under all BESS costs), indicating that the over-installation size of the wind plant can be increased when the BESS is utilized. As shown in Figs. 10(a)-(b), the reduction of the BESS cost increases the NPV and IRR because the investment cost is reduced (see Fig. 9). The NPV values in Fig. 10(a) indicate that the usage of a BESS is profitable for the over-installation sizes of 100% – 180% when the BESS cost is 50,000 and 100,000 €/MWh. However, the BESS should be used only for the over-installation sizes of 120% – 180% and 160% – 180% when the BESS cost is 200,000 and 300,000 €/MWh, respectively, because it achieves a higher NPV compared to the case where the BESS is ignored.

The NPV and IRR calculated using Problem \mathcal{P}^S are illustrated in Figs. 10(c)-(d). As expected, the NPV and IRR using Problem \mathcal{P}^S are lower compared to the corresponding NPV and IRR obtained from Problem \mathcal{P}^I (Figs. 10(a)-(b)) due to the high forecasting error of wind generation that reduces the

Figure 11: The scenario, predicted, and actual PV curves used for the performance evaluation of Problems \mathcal{P}^S and \mathcal{P}^D for 04/03/2022.

market profits. Considering the price and wind generation uncertainty, the NPV values in Fig. 10(c) indicate that the usage of the BESS is profitable only when the BESS cost is under 100,000 €/MWh because it achieves a higher NPV compared to the case where the BESS is ignored, while the maximum over-installation size that makes the project profitable is 150% – 160%. As previously mentioned, selecting the scenarios in a more sophisticated way can further enhance the performance of Problem \mathcal{P}^S and therefore can increase the NPV and IRR, especially when the BESS is considered. Note that the BESS costs are expected to fall under 200,000 €/MWh by 2030 [45], enhancing the battery profitability. Moreover, BESSs can be used to provide additional grid services to enhance their profitability; however, this is out of the scope of this work.

7.2. PV-BESS Producer

Setup. To emulate the PV power plant, we use real data from a residential PV system with an installed capacity of 4.5 kW and we upscale its power generation to consider a 8.7 MW PV plant ($\bar{P}^T = 8.7$ MW). The proposed scheme is examined under power exchange limits due to the imposed MEC limits, setting $\bar{P}^S = 6.48$ MW ($\rho = 0.74$) to consider an over-install PV power plant with nominal capacity of 134.2% of MEC. Moreover, we consider an integrated BESS with capacity of 5 MWh ($\hat{C} = 5$ MWh), charging/discharging power of 5 MW ($\bar{P}^c = \bar{P}^d = 5$ MW) and one-way efficiency of 96% ($\eta^d = \eta^c = 0.96$). Similarly with the setup of the wind producer, we set $I = E^f = 0.2\hat{C}$, $\underline{C} = 0.15\hat{C}$, and $\bar{C} = 0.95\hat{C}$. Since forecasting data are unavailable, the scenario curves for the PV generation, day-ahead energy prices and imbalance ratios are selected using Methodology 2 described in Section 5.

Performance Evaluation. The performance of Problem \mathcal{P}^S is evaluated and compared with \mathcal{P}^D for the day 04/03/2022. Figs. 11 and 6(b)-(d) depicts the real curves of the PV power generation, day-ahead prices, and imbalance ratio used in the two schemes. Note that the predicted and scenario curves are used in \mathcal{P}^S and \mathcal{P}^D , while the actual curves are used for evaluation. Figs. 12(a)-(d) and 12(e)-(h) illustrate the scheduled day-ahead decisions of the PV-BESS plant as well as the actual system operation using Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S , respectively. Figs. 12(a) and 12(e) show the predicted, actual, and scheduled PV power, indicating the high prediction error between predicted and actual generation. Figs. 12(b) and 12(f) depict the scheduled

Figure 12: The scheduled day-ahead decisions of the PV-BESS plant as well as the actual system operation using Problems \mathcal{P}^D (a)-(d) and \mathcal{P}^S (e)-(h) when the BESS degradation model is used in both optimization problems.

and actual grid power based on the PV generation and BESS power decisions shown in Figs. 12(c) and 12(g), respectively. As demonstrated in Figs. 12(g)-(h), Problem \mathcal{P}^S charges the BESS during the critical hours from 10:00 to 14:00, where the actual PV generation may exceed the MEC limits, reducing the PV curtailments from 4.24 MWh to 2.02 MWh compared to \mathcal{P}^D . Problems \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S avoid to fully charge the BESS to reduce the degradation cost (see Figs. 12(d) and 12(h)), presenting a degradation of 0.0163% and 0.0271% that corresponds to 81.35€ and 135.7€, respectively. The uncertainty-aware decisions of Problem \mathcal{P}^S increase the daily producer profit from 16447.3€ to 17203.6€ compared to \mathcal{P}^D , achieving a profit increment of 4.59%.

The execution times of \mathcal{P}^D and \mathcal{P}^S are 0.1 and 7.1 seconds, indicating that the formulated linear programs can be solved fast even when a large number of scenarios is utilized in \mathcal{P}^S .

Aggregate Performance Evaluation. Table 3 presents the total producer profits and PV power curtailments using Problems \mathcal{P}^B , \mathcal{P}^D , \mathcal{P}^S , and \mathcal{P}^I for the period 01/02/2022-30/09/2022. Problem \mathcal{P}^D reduces the PV curtailments from 551.4 MWh to 195.5 MWh and increases the profit by 3.7% compared to \mathcal{P}^B . Table 3 shows that Problem \mathcal{P}^S reduces the PV curtailments to 71.4 MWh and increases the profit by 5.0%, highlighting the

Table 3: Total actual producer profits and PV power curtailments for the period 01/02/2022-30/09/2022 using the different problems.

Problem	Profit (€)	Profit increm. (%)	PV curtail. (MWh)
\mathcal{P}^B	1,936,181		551.4
\mathcal{P}^D	2,007,600	3.7	195.5
\mathcal{P}^S	2,032,480	5.0	71.4
\mathcal{P}^I	2,106,399	8.8	21.5

superiority of the proposed stochastic scheme compared to \mathcal{P}^D . Problem \mathcal{P}^I presents total PV curtailments of 21.5 MWh, indicating that the BESS capacity is insufficient to always ensure the MEC limits. Problem \mathcal{P}^I , which is unrealizable, increases the profit by 8.8% compared to \mathcal{P}^B , indicating that Problem \mathcal{P}^S can yield even higher profits, e.g., by selecting the scenarios in a more sophisticated way and employing an operating strategy. Note that the BESS relaxation exactness is always satisfied in the simulation results, obtaining the optimal solution, for both the wind-BESS and PV-BESS producers.

Over-installation Financial Analysis. The profitability for over-installing the PV-BESS plant is investigated by calculating the IRR and NPV of the project for the PV over-installation sizes of 100%, 110%, 120%, 130%, 140%, 150%, 160%, 170%, 180%, 190%, and 200%, when the MEC limit is 8.7 MW ($\bar{P}^S = 8.7$). The annual market profits for the different over-installation sizes are calculated by solving Problems \mathcal{P}^I and \mathcal{P}^S for each day of the period 01/01/2022-31/12/2022. To calculate the NPV and IRR, we consider a total PV installation cost of 870,000 €/MW with an annual maintenance cost of 7,700 €/MW [43]. Similarly with the over-installation analysis of the wind-BESS plant in Section 7.1, we consider the same BESS costs, investment period, opportunity cost of capital, and methodology for calculating the cash flows. Fig. 13 illustrates the total investment costs for the different over-installation sizes and BESS costs.

The NPV and IRR calculated using Problem \mathcal{P}^I for the different BESS costs and over-installation sizes of the PV plant are presented in Figs. 14(a)-(b). Similarly with the over-installation analysis of the wind-BESS plant, Fig. 14(a) shows that the increment of the over-installation size of the PV plant from 100% to 160% increases the NPV from 10.3 to 13.4 million euros when the BESS is ignored, indicating the profitability of the over-installation. However, an over-installation exceeding 160% must be avoided because high PV power curtailments are applied to ensure the MEC constraints, reducing both the NPV and IRR values. As shown by the maximum NPV values in Fig. 14(a), the over-installation size of the PV plant can be increased to 170%–180% when the BESS is considered (under all BESS costs). Interestingly, the expected return on investment increases for an over-installation size of 100%–130% when the BESS is used (see Fig. 14(b)), despite the fact that the investment cost increases (see Fig. 13). Similarly with the financial analysis of the wind-BESS plant, the NPV values in Fig. 14(a) indicate that the usage of the BESS is profitable for the over-installation sizes of 100%–180% when the BESS cost is 50,000

Figure 13: The investment cost of the PV-BESS plant under different over-installation sizes when the BESS cost is 50,000, 100,000, 200,000, and 300,000 €/MWh, as well as when the BESS is ignored.

Figure 14: The NPV and IRR using Problems \mathcal{P}^I (a)-(b) and \mathcal{P}^S (c)-(d) under different over-installation sizes when the BESS cost is 50,000, 100,000, 200,000, and 300,000 €/MWh, as well as when the BESS is ignored.

and 100,000 €/MWh; however, the BESS should be used only for over-installation sizes of 120% – 180% and 140% – 180% when the BESS cost is 200,000 and 300,000 €/MWh, respectively.

The NPV and IRR calculated using Problem \mathcal{P}^S are depicted in Figs. 14(c)-(d). Although Problem \mathcal{P}^S considers the price and PV generation uncertainty that reduces the market profits and hence the NPV and IRR, Problem \mathcal{P}^S achieves a similar performance with the unrealizable Problem \mathcal{P}^I (see Figs. 14(a)-(b)). Note that Problem \mathcal{P}^S achieves a better performance for

the PV-BESS plant compared to the wind-BESS plant because the PV generation is more predictable compared to the wind generation. As shown in Fig. 14(c), the usage of the BESS is profitable for the over-installation sizes of 100% – 180% when the BESS cost is 50,000 €/MWh; however, the BESS should be used only for over-installation sizes that exceed the 120% and 140% when the BESS cost is 100,000 and 200,000 €/MWh, respectively.

8. Practical Implications

This section elaborates on the practical implementation of the proposed bidding strategy for over-install RES-BESS plants. The proposed stochastic scheme, Problem \mathcal{P}^S , can be used for the bidding strategy of a real over-install RES-BESS plants. The proposed scheme requires as input historical and/or forecasted data of the RES generation and prices to schedule the power exchange with the grid for the next day, which is submitted to the DA market. The BESS charging/discharging power set-points obtained from Problem \mathcal{P}^S should be submitted to the real plant for execution.

To create a holistic RES-BESS management system, an operating strategy is also needed along with the bidding strategy to maximize the profits in the balancing market. Specifically, the operating strategy should revise the BESS charging/discharging power set-points during the actual operation of the plant to reduce the power imbalances between day-ahead scheduled and actual power generation considering RES generation and balancing price uncertainty. The development of such an operating strategy is part of our future work.

Secure communication is a major concern in smart grid applications. Note that in real-world applications the real RES-BESS plant may be distributed far away from the central monitoring and processing unit (server or cloud-based), where the controllers of the bidding, i.e., the proposed stochastic scheme, and/or operating strategies are integrated. To achieve the practical implementation of such an advanced RES-BESS management system, an Internet of Things (IoT) system is required to facilitate the secure, over-the-internet, and bidirectional data exchange between the RES-BESS plant and the central processing unit via encrypted communication protocols (e.g., MQTT, HTTPS). Towards this direction, the following processes will take place: (a) the real plant will send periodic measurements regarding the operating conditions of the RES and BESS systems to a cloud-based time-series database; (b) the central processing unit will retrieve the latest values and historical measurements from the database, forecasting data from external services, and historical prices from the market portal to execute the proposed bidding and/or operating strategy; and (c) the decision signals (e.g., day-ahead scheduling, charging/discharging power, and RES power curtailments) will be submitted to the market and the real plant to regulate the actual operation of the RES and BESS systems.

9. Conclusions

This work develops a bidding strategy and investigates the profitability for over-install RES-BESS plants. The bidding

strategy is developed as a linear scenario-based stochastic optimization scheme that maximizes the expected profits of producers in electricity markets considering BESS degradation and MEC constraints. The proposed scheme limits the maximum power export of over-install RES plants by making BESS decisions which reduce power curtailments during the actual operation of RES-BESS plants, enhancing the producers profits. Using the proposed scheme, a financial analysis is performed to assess the profitability for over-installing hybrid RES plants by calculating the NPV and IRR metrics under different BESS costs. Simulation results indicate the ability of the approximate degradation model to generate high-quality solutions, presenting an approximation error in terms of degradation cost of 5.78% compared to the Rainflow algorithm. Simulation results also indicate the capability of the proposed stochastic scheme to yield considerably higher profits compared to the corresponding deterministic scheme. Specifically, the stochastic scheme achieves a profit increment of 5.25% and 1.23% compared to the deterministic scheme for the wind and PV producer, respectively. The financial analysis indicates that a maximum over-installation of 150% – 170% and 160% – 180% for the wind and PV plant, respectively, increases the NPV and hence is profitable when the BESS is considered. In addition, the analysis indicates that the usage of BESS is profitable when its cost is under 200,000 €/MWh. Future work will develop sophisticated methodologies for scenario generation and employ an operating strategy to further reduce RES curtailments and therefore enhance the profits of producers.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported in part by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement 101136119 (TwinEU); in part by the Research and Innovation Foundation of Cyprus under the Grant Agreement CODEVELOP-REPowerEU/1223/97 (OptimRES) through the Recovery and Resilience Facility (NextGenerationEU); and in part by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739551 (KIOS CoE - TEAMING) and from the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy.

This work also acknowledges the support of T.P. Aeolian Dynamics Ltd and H. Wise Wire Energy Solutions Limited that provided access to real-life data from wind and PV generation plants.

References

- [1] European Commission, 2050 Climate and Energy Strategy (2023).
- [2] N. Günter, A. Marinopoulos, Energy storage for grid services and applications: Classification, market review, metrics, and methodology for evaluation of deployment cases, *Journal of Energy Storage* 8 (2016) 226–234.
- [3] L. Tziouvani, L. Hadjidemetriou, S. Timotheou, Energy scheduling of wind-storage systems using stochastic and robust optimization, in: *IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting (PESGM)*, 2022, pp. 1–5.
- [4] J. M. Morales, A. J. Conejo, et al., *Integrating Renewables in Electricity Markets*, Springer, 2014.
- [5] J. M. Morales, A. J. Conejo, J. Perez-Ruiz, Short-term trading for a wind power producer, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 25 (1) (Feb. 2010) 554–564.
- [6] Commission for Regulation of Utilities, Consultation on Installed Capacity Cap (2023).
- [7] C. McInerney, D. W. Bunn, Optimal over installation of wind generation facilities, *Energy Economics* 61 (2017) 87–96.
- [8] Commission for Energy Regulation (CER), Decision on installed capacity cap (2014).
- [9] N. Padmanabhan, et al., Battery energy storage systems in energy and reserve markets, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 35 (1) (Jan. 2020) 215–226.
- [10] B. Xu, J. Zhao, T. Zheng, E. Litvinov, D. S. Kirschen, Factoring the cycle aging cost of batteries participating in electricity markets, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 33 (2) (March 2018) 2248–2259.
- [11] B. Xu, A. Oudalov, A. Ulbig, G. Andersson, D. S. Kirschen, Modeling of lithium-ion battery degradation for cell life assessment, *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid* 9 (2) (March 2018) 1131–1140.
- [12] Y. Shi, et al., A convex cycle-based degradation model for battery energy storage planning and operation, in: *Proc. IEEE Annual American Control Conference (ACC)*, 2021, pp. 4590–4596.
- [13] Liu, C. and others, A MILP-Based Battery Degradation Model for Economic Scheduling of Power System, *IEEE Trans. on Sustainable Energy* 14 (2) (April 2023) 1000–1009.
- [14] Antoniadou-Plytaria, K. and others, Market-Based Energy Management Model of a Building Microgrid Considering Battery Degradation, *IEEE Trans. on Smart Grid* 12 (2) (2021) 1794–1804.
- [15] Lee, J. and Kim, Y., Novel battery degradation cost formulation for optimal scheduling of battery energy storage systems, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 137 (2022).
- [16] N. Mahmoudi, et al., Wind power offering strategy in day-ahead markets: Employing demand response in a two-stage plan, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 30 (4) (July 2015) 1888–1896.
- [17] M. K. AlAshery, et al., Second-order stochastic dominance constraints for risk management of a wind power producer's optimal bidding strategy, *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy* 11 (3) (July 2020) 1404–1413.
- [18] L.R. Visser and others, Probabilistic solar power forecasting: An economic and technical evaluation of an optimal market bidding strategy, *Applied Energy* 370 (2024).
- [19] H. Ding, et al., Rolling optimization of wind farm and energy storage system in electricity markets, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 30 (5) (Sept. 2015) 2676–2684.
- [20] A. A. S. de la Nieta, et al., Optimal single wind hydro-pump storage bidding in day-ahead markets including bilateral contracts, *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy* 7 (3) (July 2016) 1284–1294.
- [21] R. Nourollahi, et al., Hybrid stochastic/robust offering strategy for coordinated wind power and compressed air energy storage in multielectricity markets, *IEEE Systems Journal* 16 (1) (March 2022) 977–984.
- [22] M. Liu, et al., Dispatch scheduling for a wind farm with hybrid energy storage based on wind and LMP forecasting, *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications* 51 (3) (June 2015) 1970–1977.
- [23] M. Khosravi, S. Afsharnia, S. Farhangi, Stochastic power management strategy for optimal day-ahead scheduling of wind-HESS considering wind power generation and market price uncertainties, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 134 (2022).
- [24] A. Jamali, et al., Self-scheduling approach to coordinating wind power producers with energy storage and demand response, *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy* 11 (3) (July 2020) 1210–1219.
- [25] M. Dadashi, K. Zare, H. Seyedi, M. Shafie-khah, Coordination of wind power producers with an energy storage system for the optimal participation in wholesale electricity markets, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 136 (2022).
- [26] M. Kiannejad, M. Reza-Salehizadeh, M. Oloomi-Buygi, L. Baringo, A stochastic offering approach for photovoltaic power plants in day-ahead and balancing markets, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 147 (2023).
- [27] Davide Falabretti and Francesco Gulotta and Dario Siface, Scheduling and operation of RES-based virtual power plants with e-mobility: A novel integrated stochastic model, *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 144 (2023) 108604.
- [28] Faye-Bédin, Alexandre and Blavette, Anne and Haessig, Pierre and

- Bourguet, Salvy and Daminov, Ildar, Stochastic Dynamic Programming for Energy Management of an Overplanted Offshore Wind Farm with Dynamic Thermal Rating and Storage, in: 2023 IEEE Belgrade PowerTech, 2023, pp. 01–06.
- [29] Colin, Maria Angelica Hernandez and Pilgrim, James A., Cable Thermal Risk Estimation for Overplanted Wind Farms, *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery* 35 (2) (2020) 609–617.
- [30] Anuj Kumar Rao and Pratim Kundu, System integrity protection scheme for minimizing wind curtailment considering transmission line thermal limits, *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks* 33 (2023) 100970.
- [31] C. Wolter, H. Klinge Jacobsen, L. Zeni, G. Rogdakis, N. A. Cutulis, Overplanting in offshore wind power plants in different regulatory regimes, *WIREs Energy and Environment* 9 (3) (2020).
- [32] I. Daminov, A. Blavette, S. Bourguet, H. Ben Ahmed, T. Soulard, P. Warlop, Economic performance of an overplanted offshore wind farm under several commitment strategies and dynamic thermal ratings of submarine export cable, *Applied Energy* 346 (2023).
- [33] P. Chen, T. Thiringer, Analysis of energy curtailment and capacity overinstallation to maximize wind turbine profit considering electricity price–wind correlation, *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy* 8 (4) (2017) 1406–1414.
- [34] L. Tziiovani, L. Hadjidemetriou, S. Timotheou, Successive convexification algorithms for optimizing power systems with energy storage models, *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid* 15 (2) (2024) 1807–1820.
- [35] Spanish electricity market, Day-ahead and imbalance prices (2022). URL <https://www.esios.ree.es/en>
- [36] A. J. Conejo, et al., *Decision Making Under Uncertainty in Electricity Markets*, Springer, 2010.
- [37] L. Tziiovani, et al., Energy management and control of photovoltaic and storage systems in active distribution grids, *IEEE Trans. Power Systems* 37 (3) (May 2022) 1956–1968.
- [38] C. Cassisi, et al., Similarity measures and dimensionality reduction techniques for time series data mining, in: *Advances in Data Mining Knowledge Discovery and Applications*, 2012, pp. 71–96.
- [39] Michal Kaut, Forecast-based scenario-tree generation method, *Optimization Online* (2017) 1–10.
- [40] R. Brealey, S. Myers, F. Allen, *Principles of Corporate Finance*, 10th Edition, McGraw-Hill/Irwin, 2010.
- [41] Gurobi Optimization, *Gurobi Optimizer Reference Manual* (2022). URL <http://www.gurobi.com>
- [42] M. Perez, R. Perez, K. R. Rábago, M. Putnam, Overbuilding & curtailment: The cost-effective enablers of firm PV generation, *Solar Energy* 180 (2019) 412–422.
- [43] International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), *Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2022* (2023).
- [44] V. Viswanathan, K. Mongird, R. Franks, X. Li, R. Baxter, 2022 Grid Energy Storage Technology Cost and Performance Assessment, U.S. Department of Energy (2022).
- [45] International Renewable Energy Agency, *Electricity Storage and Renewables: Costs and Markets to 2030* (2017).